

Code name	Description
Acceptability*	Patient and staff views on different components of the intervention and the intervention overall, whether they personally liked or approved of it.
Patient POV	Patient views on intervention components, distinct from their reaction to getting reminders and how it affected their behaviours, attitudes etc.
Alternate mode	Comments on the mode they prefer, comparisons between modes, advantages, and disadvantages
Face to face	
Leaflet	
Letter	
Phone call	
Staff POV (also see Fidelity - perceptions of intervention)	Staff talking about whether they liked the intervention components (and intervention overall), approved of it, thought it was appealing, including comparing one component over another. Includes why they liked that component or the intervention overall. Also includes their views on whether the intervention would be acceptable to patients.
Against the 'regimental'	Perception of the intervention as rigid or fixed, why they are for or against this
Information to hand	Perception of the information provided by the intervention, convenience, utility, benefits for the patients, other advantages
Professional role	Attitudes towards their role in intervention delivery, what they see their purpose as, thoughts on this
Return on investment ^β	Worth of the intervention in terms of numbers seen, benefits for patients, for time invested
Simplicity of the intervention ^α	Describe intervention as something simple to do, easy and therefore they found it acceptable
Appropriateness	Staff views on whether the intervention (overall and specific components) was a good 'fit' for the practice and for patients, that is do they feel the intervention was likely to achieve the intended goal, does it work with how they usually do things (value, norms) at the practice or how they usually manage patients.
Fit for patients	Whether staff felt specific components (or the intervention) were a good fit for patients and why.

Code name	Description
Different messenger, different response	Perception of the role of the messenger, how patients respond, why one staff member might be a better/worse fit than another
Message given (see Fidelity)	Whether the messages were a good fit for patients. Generally discussed as reason for tailoring the messages. Coded under 'Messages given' - 'Tailoring'.
Reach	Perceptions of the reach of the intervention, what types of patients it reached, whether it was better or worse than what they were doing usually
Suiting the mode to the patient	Matching mode of delivery to the patient, comparing modes, why one is a better/worse match than another
Fit for staff	How the intervention was received by staff (seen as fine or some resistance) and whether they felt it fit with their existing role
Fit with interest [§]	How well it fit (or not) into their own interest. See also Motivation - Specialist Interest
Fit with skillset [§]	How well it fit (or not) with their existing skills
Fit with workload [§]	How well it fit (or not) into their existing workload
Initial responses	First reaction to the intervention - see also Study Procedures - First Impressions
No say is the norm	Perception of their level of input into the decision, degree of autonomy over their role in terms of the intervention and fitting it into their work
Feasibility	
Existing opportunities and workflows**	Existing workflows, fitting the intervention in, making the most of opportunities, challenges
Conducting audit	Whether or not they were conducting an audit anyway and if this made the intervention more feasible. If no mention of feasibility, can be coded as Motivation or Appropriateness.
Fitting in the 'extra thing'	Perceptions of the intervention or specific components as something extra to routine care at the practice. what was extra and how it was feasible or not, what factors make doing something extra challenging
Patient volume matters [§]	Impact of patient numbers on feasibility of different parts of the intervention or overall.

Code name	Description
Role of practice systems [§]	Perceptions of elements of practice systems (software) or other technical infrastructure which made it more or less difficult to deliver the intervention. Distinct from processes and how they do things which is captured under fit with existing processes.
Role of protected time	How protected time was used, how it was arranged, challenges and advantages
'Slog' of the audit	Attitudes towards the audit, challenges, workload
Staff skills and coordination [§]	Staff needed and used to deliver the intervention, working together, how, and why staff were assigned to specific tasks.
Fidelity & Adaptations	Process (description) can be used to inform fidelity. Adaptations classified as mode (including, changes to ordering and how patients were targeted) and content (messages given - according to staff and patients)
Changes to mode of delivery	Changes to how the intervention was delivered organised by components. Note these changes are organised under 'Nature of modification' and 'Reason for modification'.
1. Prompts	
2. Letters	
3. Phonecalls	
4. Face to face	
5. Leaflets	
Message given	Staff describe the message given to patient in person or over the phone. Separate category for tailoring where staff explain changes to the messages given and why.
Nature of modification [¶]	Staff mention what changes they made; organised according to NATURE of adaptation specified by FRAME - tailoring, reordering, substituting, protocol drift, adding elements, removing elements
Reasons for modifying mode [¶]	Staff mention why they modified certain things in terms of the mode (any aspect outside of the message content); organised according to categories of determinant specified by FRAME - Organisation, Provider, Recipient where feasible.
Miscommunication - unclear reason	Reason for the change is unclear, may mention not understanding the intervention or picking it up wrong from researcher

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Organisation	Features of the practice itself which meant the intervention had to be modified, can include resources, the usual care/structure of care delivery (how things are done here), time
Provider	Characteristics of the HCP which led to change in delivery e.g., skills, feelings about the intervention, work norms, own preferences, or judgement (i.e., about what is best or suitable for the patient or the practice).
Recipient	Characteristics of the patient which led to intervention being modified, including the capability, access to resources, education and understanding, literacy (inc. computer literacy), readiness to engage
Access to resources	Adapting intervention to allow for fact patients may not be able to access certain resources to take part e.g., transport, computer, phone
Education and literacy	Changes to respond to patient (lack of) understanding, knowledge, literacy (computer literacy) in relation to screening or diabetes more generally
Motivation and readiness	HCPs modifying the intervention to address the fact that patients may not be motivated or prepared to attend screening or follow through on the registration
Physical capacity	
Reasons for tailoring messages	When and why HCPs adapted the messages, for which patients
Motivation	Why they took part in the study. Mapped to 'resources' (Environmental context), 'knowledge about uptake' (Knowledge), 'benefits for patients' (Beliefs about consequences), and 'Role to encourage patients' (Professional role) where possible as a priori determinants based on logic model
Benefits for patients	Belief that taking part in study will help their patients.
Knowledge about uptake	Wanting to find out how the uptake at their practice and how they are doing.
Practice resources	The role of practice resources in their decisions. Also covered practice organisation - may overlap with appropriateness and 'fit'.
Quality improvement	Wanting to use the study to improve current practice
Specialist interest	
Perceived impact	Impact on the intervention on staff and patient behaviour and attitudes. Includes patient reaction or response to the intervention, staff POV on how patient's reacted and whether/how intervention

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	influenced them, impact of the intervention on staff or the practice, and patient outcomes of registration and attendance.
Impact on staff	Impact of the intervention on staff in terms of behaviours and attitudes. Where possible coded according to output anticipated in the logic model i.e., skills in audit, new resources (register), motivation to prompt screening.
Other patient attitudes (possible determinants)	Co-existing patient attitudes which may feed into their decision to attend or not attend screening albeit not the main reason cited.
Patient outcomes	Staff views on the outcomes of the intervention (e.g., attendance and registration or patient awareness).
Attendance	Staff views on whether patients attended screening following the intervention.
Awareness	Patients describe any change in their awareness or knowledge following the intervention. If this led them to change behaviour and attend screening, then coded under Reasons for attendance - Raised awareness of risk
Non-contactable	Staff describe patients who could not be reached by intervention
Registration	Staff describe changes in terms of patient registrations
Patient reaction to reminders	How patients reacted reminders. what their thoughts and feelings were when they got the reminder in letter, by phone or face to face.
Patient POV	How patients said they reacted to reminders
Staff POV	How patients reacted to reminders according to staff.
Reasons for attendance (or intention)	
Patient POV	
Staff POV	Staff views on whether and how the intervention influenced patients to change their attitudes and/or behaviours. Note: may need to be refined further and could be integrated with Acceptability.
Reasons for non-attendance	
Patient POV	

Code name	Description
Staff POV	
Study procedures	Staff views on the briefing session, the manuals, the ongoing research support, the data collection processes and tools (i.e., audit template), the surveys, and any potential issues or recommendations. Patient views on finding out about the study, being contacted by the research team, and the information given.
Patient POV	
Acceptability	What patients thought about the study procedures, i.e., finding out about the research, the invitation letter and PIL they got from the team, and whether they found them acceptable. Also including any suggestions or changes.
Finding out about research (invitation)	What patients thought when they found out about the research study.
Information overload	
Quality of the information given	
Reasons for taking part	Why patients decided to take part
Staff POV	
Acceptability	Whether staff found different parts of the research process agreeable and why. Can include suggestions on how to improve elements of the research process.
First impressions	What they thought about the study at the start.
Getting started	
Ongoing contact	What staff thought of the ongoing contact from the researcher during the intervention period.
Study materials	
Feasibility	What was more or less feasible about the study procedures, i.e., briefing, audit template, manuals etc.
Audit template	

Code name	Description
Briefing	
Manuals	
Ongoing contact	

*overarching categories guided by implementation outcome framework [1]

^βcategories guided by the Theoretical Framework of Acceptability [2]; constructs ‘perceived effectiveness’ and ‘opportunity costs’

^αcategories guided by the Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research [3]; constructs ‘Intervention characteristics – Complexity’

[§]categories guided by potential moderators identified in the logic model

[¶]categories guided by Framework for Reporting Adaptations and Modifications-Enhanced [4]

References

- 1 Proctor EK, Powell BJ, McMillen JC. Implementation strategies: recommendations for specifying and reporting. *Implement Sci* 2013;**8**:139. doi:10.1186/1748-5908-8-139
- 2 Sekhon M, Cartwright M, Francis JJ. Acceptability of health care interventions: A theoretical framework and proposed research agenda. *Br J Health Psychol* 2018;**23**:519–31. doi:10.1111/bjhp.12295
- 3 Damschroder LJ, Aron DC, Keith RE, *et al.* Fostering implementation of health services research findings into practice: a consolidated framework for advancing implementation science. *Implement Sci* 2009;**4**:50. doi:10.1186/1748-5908-4-50
- 4 Wiltsey Stirman S, Baumann AA, Miller CJ. The FRAME: an expanded framework for reporting adaptations and modifications to evidence-based interventions. *Implement Sci* 2019;**14**:58. doi:10.1186/s13012-019-0898-y